

EEG SIGNAL BASED ON EMOTION RECOGNITION

Subhashree Behera¹, Himansu Mohan Padhy²
Sophitorium Group Of Institutions, Bhubaneswar , Orissa
India

Abstract:

This paper focuses on recognizing the emotion from human brain activity, measured by EEG signals. We have proposed a system to analyze EEG signals and classify them into different emotions (happy, sad, anger, fear etc). This system was designed using prior knowledge from other research, and is meant to assess the quality of emotion recognition using EEG signals in practice. In order to perform this task, we have gathered a dataset with EEG signals. This was done by measuring EEG signals from people that were emotionally stimulated . This method enabled us to teach our system the relationship between the characteristics of the brain activity and the emotion. We have observed different brain values(α , β , θ). We found that the EEG signals contained enough information to separate the emotion along with their attention as well as meditation capacity .

Keywords : EEG, Brain waves, Stimuli, Human-Computer Interaction

I. INTRODUCTION

Emotion also plays a crucial role in all-day communication. Emotion is omnipresent and an important factor in human life. In communication ,emotion is interpreted from the pitch of the voice or from non-verbal communication. A large part of communication is done nowadays by computer or other electronic devices. This interaction is a lot different from the way human beings interact. Interaction of computer and human being is known as human-computer interaction. Basically we can able to judge the communication by human emotions. Most of the communication between human beings involves non-verbal signs, and the social aspect of this communication is important. Measuring of exact emotion is a difficult task. A lot of research is

already done after recognizing emotions by computers. Measuring emotion from brain activity is a relatively new method. And this measurement can be done through EEG. Electroencephalography (EEG) is a relatively easy and cheap method to measure this brain activity. This paper focuses on recognizing the emotion from human brain activity, measured by EEG signals. We have proposed a system to analyze EEG signals and classify them into different emotions (happy, sad, anger, fear etc). Electroencephalography (EEG) is one effective way of recording and analyzing the brain activity due to its ease of use, affordable cost and fine resolution. Due to brain activity neurons get fired producing higher electrical potential which is recorded by the electrodes attached to the scalp of a human being. This measures differ due to varying levels of cognitive stimuli . EEG is beneficial due to high temporal resolution which helps to record variations in cognitive activity. However, EEG is sensitive to noise and used for real world life span. Here We have observed different brain values(α , β , θ). And found that the EEG signals contained enough information to separate the emotion along with their attention as well as meditation capacity and eye blinking.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

A. Human Brain

Brain is the most complex organ of human. All kind of physical tasks are led by it. It contains a neural network of 10 billion nerve cells, neurons. It handles feelings, hunger, thirst, body movements and sleep functions of human. It controls almost all the core activities required for the survival of a human. It communicates with body parts environment by sending and receiving signals. It is the core of central nervous system having brainstem, spinal cord and large brain . Spinal cord and large brain are connected through brainstem. It is divided into three different parts based on its anatomy and functionality.

Figure 1: Human Brain

Based on anatomy, brain is divided into three parts as hind brain, mid brain and forebrain. At first part, myelencephalon exists in hind brain whereas cerebellum and fourth ventricle are located above it with spinal cord. At second part, mesencephalon exists in mid brain and contains tectum, tegmentum and cerebral aqueduct. At third part, diencephalon and telencephalon exists in fore brain .

Based on functionality, brain is divided into three parts. First part is called as forebrain; also known as cerebrum or large brain and handles high level mental tasks such as computational thinking etc. Second part is called as brainstem and controls the visual functions. Third part is called as cerebellum and is responsible for body movements.

B. Electroencephalography (EEG)

Electroencephalography (EEG) is a signal representation of brain activity. The signal waves hold the valuable information about the state of brain. It is one of the non-invasive techniques for brain imaging which provides electrical potential recording for the surface of the scalp due to the electrical activity of the large collections of neurons in the brain .

Non-invasive is a technique in which the body is not invaded or cut open as during surgical investigations or therapeutic surgery. Invasive technique is opposite to non-invasive. EEG signals are defined in term of rhythmic and transient and are complex signals. Based on

frequency ranges, five types of waves can be identified. They are alpha (α), theta (θ), beta, (β), delta (δ) and gamma (γ) from low to high frequency respectively.

Brainwave Type	Frequency range	Mental states and conditions
Delta	0.1Hz to 3Hz	Deep, dreamless sleep, non-REM sleep, unconscious
beta	4Hz to 7Hz	Intuitive, creative, recall, fantasy, imaginary, dream
Alpha	8Hz to 12Hz	Relaxed, but not drowsy, tranquil, conscious
Low Beta	12Hz to 15Hz	Formerly SMR, relaxed yet focused, integrated
Midrange Beta	16Hz to 20Hz	Thinking, aware of self & surroundings
High Beta	21Hz to 30Hz	Alertness, agitation

Delta Waves (δ)

Delta waves are under the frequency range of 0 – 4 Hz. Mental states associated with these waves are deep sleep, coma or hypnosis and sometimes awake.

Figure 2.1 – Delta Wave

Theta Waves (θ)

Theta waves are under the frequency range of 4 – 8 Hz. Mental states associated with these waves are drifting thoughts, creative thinking and unconscious materials.

Figure 2.2 – Theta Wave

Alpha Waves (α)

Alpha waves are under the frequency range of 8 – 13 Hz. Mental states associated with these waves are relaxed and calm states.

Figure 2.3– Alpha Wave

Beta Waves (β)

Beta waves are under the frequency range of 13 – 30 Hz. Mental states associated with these waves are highly focused and alertness, such as during deep thinking and concentration. Beta waves are having large band of frequency as compared to others.

Figure 2.4 – Beta Waves

Gamma Waves (γ)

Gamma waves are under the frequency range of 30 Hz. Mental states associated with these are simultaneous work and multi-tasking. These waves are hard to notice due to their very low amplitude. These waves appear in each part of brain.

Figure 2.5 – Gamma Waves

C. International System of Positioning Electrodes 10/20

Although, there are several different systems (Illinois, Montreal, Aird, Cohn, Len-nox, Merlis, Oastaut, Schwab, Marshall, etc.), the 10/20 international system is the most widely used at present. To place the electrodes according to this system proceeds as follows:

The inactive or common electrode is placed remote of the skull (earlobe, nose, or chin). It is counted on data points such as: nasion and inion. Ten percent of the data points are the prefrontal and occipital planes. The rest is divided in four equal parts of 20% each.

Five cross-sectional planes exist:

- [2] Prefrontal: Fpz
- [3] Frontal: Fz
- [4] Vertex: Cz
- [5] Parietal: Pz
- [6] Occipital: Oz

III. METHODOLOGY

The work on brain computer interfaces can be divided into two parts: data acquisition and data processing.

Data acquisition -: The EEG signals were recorded using International System 10-20 with 64 electrodes placed on the scalp. We have to consider only FC1, FC2, FC3, FC4, C1, C2, C3, C4, CP1, CP2, CP3, CP4 electrodes, opening and closing left/right fist when a target appears on the screen followed by relaxation, imagining opening and closing left/right fist, opening and closing both fists, imagining opening and closing both fists. Each signal is coded as follows: T0 corresponds to the resting period, T1 corresponds to movement/movement imagery left wrist, T2 corresponds to onset of motion (real or imagined) of the right wrist. The EEG signals are sampled at 160 Hz.

Data processing:

Here the data are collected by using neuro sky mind wave mobile. It calculates all the values of electrical signals ($\theta, \beta, \alpha, \gamma$).we were calculating the values by concentrating different factors of human being :

1. Attention power
2. Meditation capacity
3. Eye blinking

Some kind of testing also performed here like speed maths test in order to know the attention capacity, burning of fire in a barrels in order to meditate on it ,etc.

IV. RESULTS

These are some of the screenshots of EEG signals of different expressions : normal, happy & sad based on the values of brain signals.

NORMAL STAGE

At normal stage, the meditation capacity goes on increasing and decreasing at certain interval of time .But remains constant from time 0-8sec that means at this point of time the person is on 100% meditation.The attention capacity is on 100% attentive at time period from 18-21secs.The eye blinking value is on constant state from time period 20secs onwards where the person doesn't blink.

HAPPY STAGE

At happy stage, the meditation capacity goes on increasing and decreasing but remains constant from time 0-8secs and from 38-50 secs that means at this point of time the person is on 100%

concentration to the state of happiness. The attention capacity is on 100% attentive position from 0-8secs,18-21secs & 38-48secs.The eye blinking value is on constant state from time period 0-10secs & 20secs onwards where the person doesn't blink.

SAD STAGE

At sad stage, the meditation capacity goes on increasing and decreasing i.e, the person is not accurately in sad state but remains constant from time 0-8secs and from 38-50 secs that means at this point of time the person is on 100% concentration to the state of sadness i.e, the person is on sad mood permanently. The attention capacity is on 100% attentive position from 0-8secs,18-21secs & 38-48secs.The eye blinking value is on constant state from time period 0-10secs & 20secs onwards where the person doesn't blink.

References

- [1] P. Zhang and D. F. Galletta, *Human-Computer Interaction and Management Information Systems: Foundations*. M.E. Sharpe, 2006.
- [2] A. C. Ramirez-Hernandez, J. A. Rivera-Bautista, A. Marin-Hernandez, and V. A. Garcia-Vega, “Detection and Interpretation of Human Walking Gestures for Human-Robot Interaction,” in *Eighth Mexican International Conference on Artificial Intelligence, 2009. MICAI 2009*, 2009, pp. 41–46.
- [3] Y.-P. Lin, C.-H. Wang, T.-L. Wu, S.-K. Jeng, and J.-H. Chen, “EEG-based emotion recognition in music listening: A comparison of schemes for multiclass support vector machine,” in *Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing, 2009. ICASSP 2009. IEEE International Conference on*, 2009, pp. 489–492.
- [4] M. Li, Q. Chai, T. Kaixiang, A. Wahab, and H. Abut, “EEG Emotion Recognition System,” in *In-Vehicle Corpus and Signal Processing for Driver Behavior*, K. Takeda, H. Erdogan, J. H. L. Hansen, and H. Abut, Eds. Springer US, 2009, pp. 125–135.
- [5] P. Rani, C. Liu, N. Sarkar, and E. Vanman, “An empirical study of machine learning techniques for affect recognition in human–robot interaction,” pp. 58–69, 2006.
- [6] T. O. Zander, C. Kothe, S. Jatzey, and M. Gaertner, “Enhancing Human-Computer Interaction with Input from Active and Passive Brain-Computer Interfaces,” in *Brain-Computer Interfaces*, D. S. Tan and A. Nijholt, Eds. Springer London, 2010, pp. 181–199.
- [7] C.-T. Lin, R.-C. Wu, S.-F. Liang, W.-H. Chao, Y.-J. Chen, and T.-P. Jung, “EEG-based drowsiness estimation for safety driving using independent component analysis,” *Circuits and Systems I: Regular Papers, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 52, no. 12, pp. 2726–2738, Dec. 2005.

- [8] B. Blankertz, M. Tangermann, C. Vidaurre, S. Fazli, C. Sannelli, S. Haufe, C. Maeder, L. Ramsey, I. Sturm, G. Curio, and K.-R. Müller, “The Berlin Brain–Computer Interface: Non-Medical Uses of BCI Technology,” *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, vol. 4, 2010.
- [9] A. Lecuyer, F. Lotte, R. B. Reilly, R. Leeb, M. Hirose, and M. Slater, “Brain-Computer Interfaces, Virtual Reality, and Videogames,” *Computer*, vol. 41, no. 10, pp. 66 – 72, Oct. 2008.
- [10] Anderson, C., Sijercic, Z, “Classification of EEG Signals from Four Subjects During Five Mental Tasks. Asymmetry During Positive and Negative Affect, Psychophysiology,” vol. 16, pp. 202–203, 1979.
- [11] C. Berka, D. J. Levendowski, M. M. Cvetinovic, M. M. Petrovic, G. Davis, M. N. Lumicao, V. T. Zivkovic, M. V. Popovic, and R. Olmstead, “Real-Time Analysis of EEG Indexes of Alertness, Cognition, and Memory Acquired With a Wireless EEG Headset,” *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 151–170, 2004.
- [12] “Psychophysiological Interaction and Empathic Cognition for Human-Robot Cooperative Work (PsyIntEC),” 10-Jul-2012. [Online]. Available: http://www.bth.se/com/gsil_cognitive_neural_eng.nsf/pages/psyintec.
- [13] T. Nykopp, “Statistical modelling issues for the adaptive brain interface,” *Helsinki University of*, 2001.
- [14] N. Kannathal, U. R. Acharya, C. M. Lim, and P. K. Sadasivan, “Characterization of EEG—A comparative study,” *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine*, vol. 80, no. 1, pp. 17–23, Oct. 2005.